

LESLLA 2025 | June 4-6, 2025

Plurilingualism Across Curriculum in Adult Basic Education: A Participatory Teacher Training-Action in Italy

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Abstract

Plurilingual approaches are increasingly applied to sustain subject learning in primary, secondary and tertiary education. However, learners in formal basic adult education remain overlooked, even though those contexts are multilingual in terms of class composition and dynamics. The paper presents participatory action research conducted in Italy that aimed to introduce plurilingual and intercultural approaches into adult basic education curricula. It focused on leveraging learners' full linguistic repertoires to enhance subject learning and language and metalinguistic awareness. Five plurilingual teaching tools in subject areas were developed and piloted across diverse classes, promoting cooperative learning, mediation, and critical engagement. We outline the history tool as an example to show how it facilitated intercultural and plurilingual perspectives in the study of the post-Second World War period. Teachers and students reported positive impacts on engagement, understanding, and class dynamics. The advantages of systematically adopting plurilingual approaches across curriculum subjects were confirmed, though further studies and resources are needed to sustain plurilingual education in similar contexts.

Keywords: plurilingualism, adult education, curriculum subjects, Italy

Introduction

There has been a steady increase in interest in pedagogical approaches leveraging learners' linguistic repertoires to support learning and overcome the obstacles that children and adults who speak a language other than the school language may encounter. These approaches include various theoretical, methodological, and pedagogical stances, such as translanguaging (García & Wei, 2014), the so-called “pluralistic approaches”, which, in turn, encompass a series of different approaches (Candelier et al., 2012, 2013), or the content and language integrated learning (CLIL) as a specific approach within bilingual education (Marsh, 1994).

Developed from different perspectives and within different educational traditions, these approaches nevertheless share essential traits (Blanchet, 2021; Cognigni, 2020; Cummins, 2021; Galante et al., 2022; García, 2017; García & Otheguy, 2019; Moore et al., 2020; Pugliese & Zanoni, 2026; Sierens & Van Avermaet, 2013; Smythe, 2023; Vallejo & Dooly, 2019). Together, they shape what has been defined as “a major paradigmatic change” (Candelier et al., 2013, p. 9) or the “multilingual turn in language education” (Conteh & Meier, 2014), which has brought important innovations to pedagogical practices that pursue inclusive education. In this study, we focus on common aspects and use the term “plurilingual approaches” to refer to all pedagogic approaches that draw on learners' linguistic repertoires and the spontaneous plurilingual dynamics emerging in classrooms.

Plurilingual approaches in classroom practice have been experimented with for decades. From a non-exhaustive overview of the vast literature on the topic, it appears that these approaches have been implemented experimentally in pre-school, primary, secondary, and tertiary education. Basic adult education in formal educational settings and vocational training has been almost neglected, although the few practices documented so far have proved to result in greater ease of learning, increased learner wellbeing and self-assertion in their linguistic identities (Beiler & Dewilde, 2023; CEDEFOP - Centre européen pour le développement de la formation professionnelle, 2020; Kaiper-Marquez, 2023; Meier & Styger, 2023; Mustonen & Strömmer, 2024).

This paper reports the rationale and results of a participatory teacher-training action research aimed at introducing plurilingualism as both a stance and a practice into basic adult education in formal educational settings and in vocational training, with a focus on adult education classes. The action centred on the learning and teaching of curricular subjects, and involved teachers of subjects (including Italian as a curricular language) and teachers of Italian L2 for migrants.

In proposing a plurilingual approach across the curriculum, we referred to the *Guide for the development and implementation of curricula for plurilingual and intercultural education* issued by the Council of Europe (Beacco et al., 2016a; Beacco et al., 2016b), which develops the notion of plurilingualism as expressed in the *Common European Framework* (Council of Europe, 2001; hereafter the CEFR) into curricular proposals. A plurilingual and intercultural approach, transversal to all subjects, recognises that the linguistic dimension cuts across the curriculum and thus calls on all teachers to contribute to the development of learners' plurilingual and pluricultural competence. Without denying the specificity of their disciplines, subject teachers can help students to understand and master the language of these, encouraging each student to draw on their entire linguistic repertoire, which becomes a resource for the entire class. Since it aims to foster each student's awareness and development of their linguistic repertoires and resources, it considers all

students, regardless of their migratory or non-migratory background or whether they speak majority, minority, or heritage languages (Beacco et al., 2016a).

The participatory teacher-training action research centred on developing and piloting practical teaching tools designed to help teachers implement a plurilingual approach to language and subject teaching, which will be further described in the following sections.

The Participatory Action Research

Background and Participants

The action research was promoted by the Metropolitan City of Bologna and the ‘Gian Franco Minguzzi’ institution, which launched an extensive pluriennial teacher training programme (2018-today) through three projects to sustain plurilingualism in the public educational system of the Metropolitan area, from pre-school to adult education, and in the public/private vocational training system (Ameli et al., 2019; Centro RiEsco, 2025; Minuz, 2022).

The project we present here, ‘Lingue prime e plurilinguismo nell’educazione degli adulti e nella formazione professionale’¹ (2023-2024), was built on the results of the previous steps and responded to the request from the aforementioned institution to focus on adult education and to include vocational training. Specifically, it responded to the need that the previous training path had brought to light: a more radical adoption of a multilingual approach, capable of moving from the initial recognition and occasional promotion of learners’ languages and translanguaging practices to their systematic and strategic use in teaching and learning subjects (Minuz, 2022).

The project involved 11 classes from three Adult Education Centres (hereinafter CPIA), two in urban areas, one in a mountain area, for a total of 231 students and 14 teachers². Among the CPIA courses, on which we focus in this article, 7 were aimed at obtaining the first-cycle diploma (‘First educational cycle’, corresponding to ISCED³ 1-2), and 4 at the certificate attesting to the acquisition of basic skills relating to compulsory education, also covering the subjects common to all vocational school courses (‘First educational cycle’, ISCED 2-3) (MIUR – Ministero dell’Istruzione, dell’Università e della Ricerca, 2015). The fourteen CPIA teachers taught the following subjects: Italian (curricular subject); languages (English), history and social studies; mathematics and science; Italian as a second language. All had solid experience with plurilingual, heterogeneous classes of young adults and adults, were aware of the plurilingual turn in education, and some of them had already occasionally adopted plurilingual practices and teaching strategies to move from monolingual to plurilingual education (Table 1).

¹‘First languages and plurilingualism in Adult Education and Vocational training’.

² This article focuses on the CPIA and does not report on the outcomes of the project in the vocational training centre.

³ International Standard Classification of Education

Table 1.*Schools, teachers, students and classes involved*

School	No. teachers	No. students	Courses and subjects
CPIA 2 metropolitano di Bologna “Eduard C. Lindemann”	7	115	First didactic cycle, ISCED 1-2. Italian, history, geography; Italian for foreign learners, mathematics and science, English. 3 classes
			First didactic cycle, ISCED 2-3 Italian, history, mathematics and science, English 2 classes
CPIA “Montagna” di Castel di Casio	3	84	First didactic cycle, ISCED 1-2. Italian, history, geography; Italian for foreign learners, mathematics and science 2 classes
			First didactic cycle, ISCED 2-3 Italian, history, mathematics and science, English 2 classes
CPIA “Silver Sirotti” di Forli-Cesena	4	32	First didactic cycle, ISCED 1-2. Italian, history, geography; Italian for foreign learners, mathematics and science 2 classes

The classes in the CPIAs were highly diverse in terms of learners’ languages, countries of origin, ages, and schooling/literacy levels. For example, in the CPIA “Montagna”, the first cycle class was attended by 28 participants from 14 countries (including Italy), aged 16 to 59, with 3 to 11 reported years of schooling. Students speaking other languages had levels of communicative language competence ranging from Pre-A1 to B1 of the *CEFR Companion Volume* (Council of Europe, 2020). More than half of all students reported being bilingual.

Objectives and Methodology

‘First languages and plurilingualism in Adult Education and Vocational training’ was a participatory action research project (Chevalier & Buckles, 2019; Orefice, 2006) with the

overarching objective of improving the quality of educational provision in settings characterised by high linguistic diversity and a high proportion of students with a migration background.

To this end, the project aimed to facilitate knowledge building by/for all students by recognising, activating, and developing their linguistic repertoires. It responded to the participant teachers' positive attitude towards an active and aware plurilingualism in the classrooms that had emerged in previous projects and in other Italian adult education centres (Cheffy et al., 2021; Minuz et al., 2020). The previous training projects also highlighted teachers' need for guidance in adopting plurilingual approaches.

The project was centred on the production, controlled piloting, discussion, and validation of innovative, plurilingual teaching tools for the systematic implementation of plurilingual approaches in curriculum subjects. It was conducted through interaction between the researchers, teacher trainers, teachers, and learners. This design was consistent with the perspective that collaboration between researchers and teaching professionals promotes sustainable pedagogical innovation to the greatest extent. Specifically, the interaction aimed at co-constructing knowledge for a teaching approach grounded in research results and teachers' reflective experience (Horner, 2016; Opstoel et al., 2024; van Schaik et al., 2019).

The action research was conducted from February to November 2024, following the phases and methodology summarised in Table 2.

Table 2.

Phases, actions and methodology

Phase	Actions and methodology
1. Planning Nov. 2023-Feb. 2024	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Definition of subjects and timetable with teachers and school directors/course coordinators. • Teachers' adherence on a voluntary basis. • Training session to finalise objectives and tasks. • Data collection on classes: student numbers, countries of origin, ages, and previous schooling (questionnaire). • Students' linguistic repertoires survey (through a questionnaire compiled by students with teachers' guidance).
2. Development of the tools March-May 2024	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 5 sample tools developed by researchers with extensive experience in teaching in adult education and vocational training, considering the information collected in phase 1
3. Piloting of the tools May-June 2024	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tools piloted by teachers integrated into their regular course plan in two CPIAs.
4. Validation of the tools (first cycle) May-June 2024	<p>Qualitative methodology:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ethnographic classroom observation during the piloting. • Collection of learners' written and oral outputs for the tasks. • A student satisfaction questionnaire.

5. Data analysis and first revision of the tools Oct.-Nov. 2024 ⁴	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A focus group with the teachers after the piloting phase. • Data analysis. • Tools revised. • Development of “Suggestions for the Teachers” based on the validation results.
6. Validation of the tools (second cycle) and finalisation of the tools	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tools piloted by teachers external to the core research group in a third CPIA • Ethnographic classroom observation during the piloting. • A focus group with the teachers after the piloting phase. • Tools finalised for publication.

The outcomes described and discussed in this paper are based on data collected in phase 4 through classroom observations, teachers’ focus groups, and samples of learners’ written production.

For the classroom observation, a specially designed data collection sheet was used. In addition to information on the lesson (e.g., participants, topic), the sheet recorded students’ responses to the teaching proposal, the comprehensibility and clarity of the instructions, and if and how the teaching materials fostered classroom interaction and participation. The sheet guided classroom observation through indicators of students’ interest in the proposed plurilingual activities, understanding of the tasks, and active participation. The indicators are based on observable behaviours that can be interpreted as signals (Lomholt & Qvortrup, 2025; Pontecorvo, 2005). For example, the indicators of engagement in activities focused on language included:

- showed interest in researching the topic in their language (e.g. the recipe) using accessible sources (websites, YouTube, etc.);
- consulted their classmates regarding linguistic aspects;
- discussed the topic with classmates from the same country of origin (if present in the class);
- were very focused on the task at hand.

Notes compiled independently by the observers also recorded additional elements useful for assessing the class’s reception of the teaching proposals, teachers’ strategies, and adaptations of the tools to the class’s needs.

Two one-hour focus groups involved all teachers. The online video-recorded sessions were first transcribed with Transkriptor (<https://transkriptor.com>), then revised in accordance with HIAT conventions for speech transcription (*HIAT-Halbinterpretative Arbeitstranskriptionen*, see Rehbein et al., 2004).

The focus group transcripts and the observation notes were then inductively (content-driven) coded according to three parameters: topic, evaluative comments, and suggestions, then compared and analysed (Cardano, 2011). Given the low response rate to the student questionnaire, data from it were used to supplement these findings.

⁴ A second round of validation, in November 2025, involved teachers from different geographical areas and without prior training.

During piloting, students produced (individually, in pairs, or in groups) 233 plurilingual items as outcomes of the tasks suggested in the tools. The materials range from notes taken in class to multilingual digital books, comparative historical charts, multilingual glossaries, video recordings, menus, and dietary guidelines (see below, “The Tools”). We defer the analysis of this diverse and substantial corpus to a later stage of the research. For the time being, we regard the materials produced as an encouraging sign of interest in multilingual tasks and of the applicability of multilingual teaching approaches in adult education. The research we present here aimed to answer three questions:

1. Do tools such as those piloted have potential effectiveness in promoting plurilingualism as a systematic approach to teaching?
2. In general, is the intentional and strategic mobilisation of learners’ linguistic repertoires in learning school curriculum subjects workable in the context of basic adult education?
3. How do participants in the educational process respond to teaching practices inspired by plurilingual approaches?

In the next pages, we provide a description of the tools, their conceptualisation, and piloting; the results of the action research and the data analysis are integrated into this narrative. Questions 1 and 2 are addressed in the section ‘The Teaching Tools’ and ‘An Example: History’, respectively. The third question will be addressed only briefly in the section “Teachers’ evaluation”.

The Teaching Tools

Methodological Background and Teaching Approach

The five teaching tools developed are sample materials, piloted by and subsequently discussed with teachers, in order to generate further new and different tools. The consultation with the teachers led to the development of five content-based tools for the following three curricular axes in the CPIAs and two vocational courses:

- i. *Language and historical-social axis*
Stories of women who changed the world: plurilingual storytelling (Frida Kahlo, Wangari Muta Maathai).
- ii. *Historical-social axis*
A history lesson with a plurilingual and comparative approach.
- iii. *Mathematical-scientific axis*
A healthy diet.
- iv. *Kitchen, dining hall and bar*
A mix of cuisines.
- v. *Electrical system*
Electrician-Electricity-Electrical energy.

Since the tools are intended to be generative models, teachers had the option of adapting them to fit the pace and needs of the class, provided that they kept track of the modifications made and the reasons for them. Changes and adaptations were later considered in the revision. Four dimensions had to be considered in developing the tool:

1. The plurilingual approaches and the different practices they suggest. The encompassing vision we adopted enabled us to model teaching proposals developed from different perspectives;
2. The heterogeneity of the classes, according to origin, language, previous schooling, literacy competence, familiarity with formal/academic language registers, subject knowledge and competence;
3. A plurilingual curriculum, which recognises the linguistic dimension of all curriculum subjects and considers all languages in the classroom as a learning resource;
4. The context of adult and young adult education, that is, formal educational settings geared towards recognised certification.

In heterogeneous classes, difference is the key parameter in managing individual learning and educational relationships in the context of inclusive teaching (Lawrence-Brown, 2020; Tomlinson, 1999). The tools focus on literacy-related, linguistic and cultural heterogeneity; classes are considered as complex systems in which various continua of language and literacy competences intersect (Caon, 2006; Coste, 2010; Marderness, 2020) and, especially in adult education, different kinds of knowledge and learning paradigms, such as experiential and school-based knowledge, coexist (Bultynck & Vanbuel, 2017; DeCapua & Marshall, 2015; Vogl, 2019).

The formal educational context requires that students achieve at least functional literacy, as well as subject knowledge and competence, to meet institutional objectives. The teaching materials had to consider both objectives in order to provide helpful support to the teachers.

In understanding and producing written texts, for example, this twofold objective can be broken down into the following actions, at least (Kurvers et al., 2015; Minuz et al., 2022; Oakhill et al., 2014; Verhoeven & Perfetti, 2017):

- consolidating technical literacy skills;
- automatising decoding processes and increasing fluency (orthographic reading skills, morpheme-based reading, synthesising words into sentences, etc.);
- automatising writing processes and increasing fluency;
- developing reading and writing strategies, metalinguistic awareness, and lexical, morphosyntactic and textual competence;
- consolidating oral skills;
- developing a positive attitude towards reading, literacy practices, and familiarity with the written language;
- becoming familiar with formal and academic language registers.

For students with a migrant background and low competence in Italian, the development of L2 communicative language competence and the growth of their ability to orient themselves in Italian society/culture are additional objectives.

Each tool has two interwoven teaching pathways. The first is designed to assist critical content alongside academic/formal language acquisition. To this end, the tool suggests linguistic and cognitive facilitation and scaffolding techniques in subject teaching and learning to enable understanding of concepts and notions, based on extensive experience in the Italian school system (Grassi et al., 2003; LIFOP (Lingua Italiana per la Formazione Professionale⁵), 2001; Minuz, 2006; Pallotti, 2000; Scataglini, 2017; Zambelli, 2014).

⁵Italian Language for Vocational Training'; the acronym is the title of a monographic issue of the review *Quaderni di Formazione* 80.

The second pathway aims to develop each student's linguistic repertoire and the awareness of their linguistic resources. Activities based on the strategic mobilisation of both the class's and each student's languages aim to develop awareness of their plurilingual and intercultural competences. Most of the teaching proposals can be framed in terms of mediation, defined as the communicative language activity by which

the user/learner acts as a social agent who creates bridges and helps to construct or convey meaning, sometimes within the same language, sometimes across modalities (e.g. from spoken to signed or vice versa, in cross-modal communication) and sometimes from one language to another (cross-linguistic mediation). (Council of Europe, 2020, p. 90)

Mediation activities imply the co-construction of meaning from linguistic, as well as social and cultural, perspectives; they may regard texts, concepts, and communication. Mediating texts through (informal) translation or interpretation, paraphrases, summaries, and other techniques of text reformulation play an important role in the linguistic functioning of society, in every domain. "Mediating concepts, that is, facilitating access to knowledge and concepts for others, is a fundamental aspect of parenting, mentoring, teaching and training, but also of collaborative learning and work" (Council of Europe, 2020, p. 91). Mediating communication "aims to facilitate understanding and shape successful communication between users/learners who may have individual, sociocultural, sociolinguistic or intellectual differences in standpoint" (Council of Europe, 2020, p. 91). In this sense, mediation is at the core of education (Coste & Cavalli, 2015).

The tools suggest various teaching strategies to encourage, observe, and reflect on the mediation activities implemented and, more generally, on forms of plurilingual communication within the class. In fact, alongside structured tasks such as the one presented below ("An Example: History"), the teacher guide included in each tool and "Suggestions for adopting a plurilingual approach", which are an integral part of the tools, encourage teachers to make space for spontaneous plurilingual communication within the classroom, to value it and incorporate it into their teaching plan (Pugliese, 2017). This communication could include translation of words, reformulation of a text or a teacher's utterance, and intercomprehension, "a form of communication in which each person uses his or her own language and understands that of the other" (Doyé, 2005, p. 7; Bonvino & Garbarino, 2022; Strathmann, 2025). Instances of intercomprehension, for example, between Urdu- and Punjabi-speaking students, were observed during piloting. Moreover, a task based on this approach was proposed and piloted in one tool: students read a simple text in Spanish, a language no one in the class knew. The following group discussion raised interesting reflections on the linguistic features and cognitive strategies that enabled their comprehension.

Research and transnational evidence-based curricula highlight the positive effects of plurilingual approaches on the development of language and metalinguistic awareness, and promote a teaching aimed explicitly at enhancing them (Beacco et al., 2016a; Candelier et al., 2012, 2013; Cenoz & Gortez, 2022; Vallejo & Dooly, 2019). Consistent with this, the tools propose structured tasks that reflect either on language diversity and characteristics (language awareness) or on specific aspects, such as orthography, grammar, and lexis (metalinguistic awareness). In other words, the tools prompt the use of the languages from the students' repertoires as a medium for talking about language and as a resource for identifying cross-linguistic

correspondences (Woll et al., 2022). Lexical and grammatical observations may occur in learners' languages and in Italian to report the results of the comparison to the class.

As for classroom management, an approach that favours peer and cooperative learning (such as project work, pair or group work) has been confirmed to be more effective with adults (Korpela, 1992; Nevin, 1989; Tran et al., 2019). Since most studies focus on the impact of plurilingual communication and/or translanguaging on the acquisition of an additional language, as noted above, further studies on the relation among peers and cooperative learning, plurilingual communication and subject learning by adults are needed.

The highly heterogeneous classes required careful design of the tools. The first, more general consideration concerns respect for both students' linguistic choices in relation to their self-representation as plurilingual adults and the complexity and stratification of their repertoires, to avoid assigning restricted identities based on their "mother tongue". Thus, for example, learners whose language of schooling does not coincide with their family/heritage language may prefer (some did, others did not) to use the former, especially if they have only oral knowledge of the latter or if this is an unwritten language. Others may opt for an additional language other than that of their schooling (Italian in our project), prioritising being understood by their classmates.

A further point of attention is the involvement of the entire class. As we have already said, a plurilingual and intercultural curriculum concerns not only students with a migrant background but all students (Beacco et al., 2016a). In our case, Italian-speaking students were invited to complete the tasks in an additional language of their choice (usually English or French), using sources in that language when appropriate. Moreover, they were enabled to participate in metalinguistic tasks to consolidate their competence in Italian or in the study of the curricular additional languages.

Diversity in language competence and in subject knowledge does not, of course, go hand in hand. The tools seek to convey a vision of the class as a dynamic system in which language, knowledge and experience can intersect in a flexible and respectful way.

Outline of the Tools

Structure

The tools are centred on a subject topic and have a modular structure, allowing flexible use according to students' needs, teachers' planning, and local dynamics in the development of the lesson. Modules can be presented sequentially, following the suggested order, or in the order best-suited to the particular context; teachers can use all of them or a selection in line with class needs.

Each module contains:

- visuals and oral and/or written texts that are graduated according to language competence levels to meet the needs of heterogeneous classes;
- individual, group and whole class oral and written tasks in Italian and languages of the students' repertoires;
- plurilingual and intercultural tasks;
- cross-linguistic comparative tasks (metalinguistic tasks), and language-focused tasks.

Format

The tools have the following standard format:

1. *Introduction*. This describes the intended target group(s), curriculum subject, objectives, plurilingual tasks, resources, timing, and assessment instruments.

2. *Teacher guide*. Suggests how to use the tools to foster plurilingual communication and presents additional resources.
3. *Classroom materials*. Contains task prompts and exercises for students.

The appendix “Suggestions for adopting a plurilingual approach”, based on the results of the focus group and relevant literature, provides further empirical guidelines for ensuring continuity and consistency in plurilingual teaching activities.

For each area the tools aim to develop, specific objectives are identified and described with reference to relevant national and European documents, namely:

- for subject learning, the national and regional curricula (MIUR, 2015; Regione Emilia-Romagna, 2022);
- for plurilingual and intercultural competence, the FREPA/CARAP⁶ descriptors (Candelier et al., 2012, 2013);
- for mediation activities, the CEFR Companion volume descriptors (Council of Europe, 2020);
- for communicative language competence, as above (Council of Europe, 2020);
- for linguistic competence and metalinguistic awareness, the inventories in *Profilo della lingua italiana* (Spinelli & Parizzi, 2010).

Objectives for plurilingual and intercultural competences refer to knowledge, attitude and skills necessary to act in multilingual and multicultural contexts. They allow for measurement of the increase in awareness of linguistic and cultural diversity, positive attitude towards other languages and cultures and the ability to manage diversity, such as, for example, “Can use knowledge and skills already mastered in one language in activities of comprehension/production in another language” (Candelier et al., 2012, 2013).

An Example: History

History in an Intercultural and Plurilingual Perspective

Teaching history in heterogeneous adult education classes poses several challenges. First of all, teaching history in a multicultural environment means adopting others’ perspectives and breaking with a linear, nation- and Eurocentric narrative to move, instead, towards a world history that highlights connections and exchanges among cultures (Appadurai, 1996; Perillo, 2010). This kind of teaching questions the core concepts connected with values, visions, and institutions, to which one refers with terms that may be translatable, only apparently translatable, or untranslatable. History revolves around persons, objects, places and events that may be unknown. From a linguistic perspective, this requires the progressive acquisition of formal, academic registers, which present less frequent vocabulary and grammatical structures, for example, in Italian, the use of the past simple (“passato remoto”).

The National Curriculum for Adult Education (MIUR, 2015) envisages an intercultural approach in history teaching. The competence a learner should reach is that of “Orienting oneself in the complexity of the present by understanding historical, geographical and social facts from the past, also in order to engage with different opinions and cultures” (MIUR, 2015, pp. 39-40). The curriculum mentions the ability to “Make comparisons between different areas of the world” among the skills underpinning this competence; the “Concepts of democracy, justice, equality,

⁶ Framework of Reference for Pluralistic Approaches to Languages and Cultures: Competences and resources/Cadre de Référence pour les Approches Plurielles des Langues et des Cultures

citizenship and civil rights”, as well as “Essential aspects of the history of one’s own environment” are given as crucial pieces of knowledge.

Classroom Implementation

The tool is organised into four modules, which we present briefly below, along with examples of the piloting results. Piloting teachers followed the suggested pathway below:

Module 1 – Ice-breaking approaches the topic ‘The liberation from Fascism and the birth of the Italian Republic (1945-1948)’. The teacher’s guide suggests a brainstorming session on civil national festivities in Italy and in learners’ countries, starting from a poster celebrating Liberation Day (25 April).

Module 2 – Approaching the history textbook introduces the subject topic and focuses on students’ ability to deal with academic language.

Students read a chapter from a CPIA history textbook, which is already written in simplified language. The text is presented through various techniques to meet different learners’ levels of written comprehension: oral presentation, facilitated versions, visuals, and scaffolding questions.

Students focus on vocabulary to progressively co-construct a plurilingual glossary. Figure 1 illustrates the contributions of a student from the Ivory Coast with four years of schooling and speaking Konyanka, Maninka, and French (see “Teachers’ evaluation” below for a discussion of the table).

Figure 1.

A contribution to the history glossary

MATERIALE E

Costa d'Avorio
KONYAKA

Tabella A - Le parole della storia

Parole in italiano	Lingua francese	Lingua... KOXACA	Lingua...	Lingua...
Economia	ECONOMI	bla il-IO MAN		
Trasporti marittimi	TRANSPORT	MANBI SALAO		
Trasporti ferroviari	TRANSPORT	MANBI SALAO		
Disoccupati	BESOCUPE	NÈ FOHILA		
Governo	GOVERNE	KOUNIOI		
Referendum				
Assemblea costituente	ranssemble	ladje		
Monarchia	MONARCHIE	MONAR HIO		
Repubblica	Republic			
Partito	Parti	LAEA TAKA		
Costituzione	costitusion	doutt conmence		

Module 3 – Let us compare our histories aims to co-construct a comparative historical table of events at the end of the Second World War and/or leading to the independence of their countries.

Students look for information in sources in any of their languages. Students report orally to the class in Italian, produce a written summary of the key information in Italian (Figure 2), fill in the table, and orally discuss the research results. The teacher posts the table on the class platform as learning material. Figure 2 shows the summary written by a student with interrupted schooling who attended a 60-hour course in literacy and Italian before enrolling at the CPIA.

Figure 2.

*Italian summary*⁷

IL MIO PAESE È GUINEA CONAKRO CAPITALÈ CONAKRO
 È NATA NEL 1958 LIBERA DALLA FRANCIA
 IL CAPO È STATO TOURE HA È STATO UN DITTATORE
 PER MOLTI ANNI PIU' DI 20 ANNI

Module 4 – Reflecting on language(s) focuses on the linguistic means needed to express the notion of the past in a cross-linguistic comparison. Students observe the verb forms in the chapter read (Figure 3).

Figure 3.

Visualisation of the sequence of events

The class discusses how learners' languages realise the notion of the past; the teacher prompts reflections with questions such as, "In your language(s), do you use special words when

⁷ My country is Guinea Conakry capital is Conakry / it was born in 1958 free from France / the leader was Toure but he was a dictator for many years more than twenty years.

you talk about the past?” Students give oral examples, write (when possible) relevant sentences on the board, read them aloud and compare them with the use of Italian past tenses.

The module enhances both students’ use of past tenses, particularly among those with lower proficiency in Italian, and narrative competence among all students.

The various challenges that teaching history presents in heterogeneous adult classes might lead one to believe that a plurilingual approach to this subject would introduce an unmanageable level of complexity. However, although documented here only by a few written examples drawn from the collected corpus, the approach has proven feasible. While demonstrating its effectiveness requires a targeted assessment procedure, its feasibility (see the research questions above) has been confirmed first and foremost.

Teachers’ Evaluation

Since this paper focuses on teaching materials and strategies that facilitate the strategic and conscious use of linguistic and cultural resources by all students, in this section, we limit our report to teachers’ feedback on these after the piloting. We will not discuss here the values and representations that teachers connect with plurilingual stances, nor the linguistic ideologies that underlie them, though these did emerge during the validation process (for these aspects, see Pugliese et al., in print).

Teachers’ feedback on the piloted tools was positive. They highlighted specific adjustments they made while using them and suggested further improvements, such as stronger modularity and ways to bridge activities across modules. On the whole, they valued the layout and activities of the tools and felt supported in adopting a plurilingual approach in subject teaching. From the focus group (Table 2), some strengths emerged as broadly agreed on.

Addressing subject content through different methods, including studying in each learner’s family or school language and mediation, resulted in easier learning and teaching, since attention could focus on concept elaboration. *Easier, relaxing, engaging, and enjoyable* were terms that students also used in their feedback (Pugliese et al., in print).

By observing learners reading in their own languages, teachers were able to gain a better understanding of the cognitive and strategic resources students drew upon, which often remain invisible or underemployed in adult basic education, as one teacher observed:

(T11) I delved a bit deeper into textual competence. And so, it was very interesting for me because when they worked on the texts—in their own languages, since most of them chose to work in their own languages—I really saw their level of schooling, which is something we’re aware of. But I realised that in their own languages, they underlined and circled the key words. So it was also helpful to understand their study method, which seems, when they do Italian, to be a bit blocked, so to speak. [...] And then there was great enthusiasm about being allowed to read the texts in their own languages.

The tools enabled the systematic activation of individual and class language resources beyond the implementation of the suggested activities. They also supported positive classroom dynamics through mediation practices. As noted by teachers and observers, spontaneous

plurilingual dynamics could emerge, become visible and consolidate, such as translation and intercomprehension, between speakers of related languages.

Guided interlinguistic comparisons at the individual and group levels facilitate the development of language and metalinguistic awareness between Italian and other language speakers. It has a further empowerment effect, as a teacher commented:

(T4) this activity in particular showed me that [comparing languages] is very useful even at a lower level, where it is very difficult to raise metalinguistic awareness emphasising the mother tongue is like recognising a skill that even the students themselves are not aware of.

Students and teachers alike gained a stronger awareness of language diversity. Activities such as didactic, non-professional translation, for example, drew attention to phenomena such as semantic shifts across languages, and lexical borrowing, as well as to differences at the grammatical and textual levels. The Italian – French – Konyanka glossary (Figure 1) provides an insight into the lexical strategies employed by the student. If we set aside the formal correctness of the French words – which are likely only orally known and whose orthography is clearly modelled on Italian – we can notice that the choice of equivalents for the Italian words highlights an exchange between Italian and French. Although the direction (from French to Italian or vice versa) cannot be clearly defined, the class discussion of this exchange led to a deeper understanding of the conceptual content, as well as to a more specific lexical competence.

Allowing sources in different languages and reports interlinguistically mediated by students to enter the lesson space facilitates the intercultural approach to subjects that some teachers intend to pursue further. It results in a cultural comparison beyond stereotypes, it was said. Regarding the history tool presented above, a teacher commented:

(T5) It was very useful for history. The plurilingual perspective was helpful because it allowed for a discussion that would not normally take place in Italian, because in Italian we talk about... well, we tend to talk less about other countries than about our own, and in any case, from a Eurocentric perspective. Instead, this shifted the focus. So, there was more participation, even from those who usually participate less, precisely because of language barriers.

The emphasis on pair/group work and cooperative learning, along with the flipped roles between teachers and learners, resulted in effective learning and empowerment. The majority of participants (n=9) stressed that this was particularly true with vulnerable learners, such as unaccompanied minor refugees and adults with precociously interrupted schooling.

Plurilingual approaches underpin a vision of adult education that emphasises learner autonomy and cooperative learning, thereby redefining the teacher's role. A multilingual environment may jeopardise the teacher's role in a way that is different and more profound than when there is just one language of education, since the teacher may not be able to control either the reliability of the learners' sources or the correctness of the report, as one teacher observed. Different forms of educational quality control, such as peer discussion, the use of digital supports (e.g., translators), and the counselling of cultural mediators, are among the suggested solutions.

The accessibility, quality and adequacy of sources in the students' languages should be addressed, according to some teachers. School and scientific texts are not equally accessible across languages, and Italian schools may lack the skills to assess their quality or adequacy for students' linguistic and cognitive needs. For example, students with interrupted schooling may have difficulties in understanding the academic register of their own languages. During piloting, teachers overcame this problem through teaching strategies such as group work and the invitation to resort to oral sources, such as language community members.

Comments like those reported above indicate that certain conditions at the organisational and ecological levels are needed to develop plurilingual teaching to its full potential. A stronger presence of cultural and linguistic mediators, both professionals and community members, would support teachers and learners. It would be desirable to equip the school with a library—perhaps a virtual one—available to students and teachers, possibly in collaboration with the communities and countries of origin. Furthermore, some participants in the focus groups stressed the need for collaboration between teachers of non-linguistic and linguistic subjects, as well as between teachers of different curricular languages. The intertwining of subject competences and disciplinary languages enables a coherent teaching approach that best promotes students' strategic use of their linguistic and cognitive resources.

Digital tools, especially online translators and increasingly AI, are valuable resources for students in multilingual environments. However, they can sometimes become shortcuts that may hinder rather than help learning, as some teachers complained. Examples of this “misuse” signalled by some teachers are in the implementation of the task of completing a comparative table as originally proposed in the tool “A history lesson”, where some students just copied the Italian digital translation of a text in their chosen languages, instead of using the source to produce an original summary like that in Figure 2. The impact of technological aids in adult education in multilingual settings deserves closer investigation, with a view to encouraging their critical use to further knowledge acquisition.

Conclusions

The teachers saw plurilingual approaches as a valid response, although not yet systematic, to the issues they encounter in their daily teaching practice with adults and young adults in CPIAs and vocational training.

“First languages and plurilingualism in Adult Education and Vocational training” project confirmed that designing a plurilingual and intercultural curriculum for adult education, as for other areas of the education system, could have high innovative potential. It also confirmed the need for specific training and guidance for teachers, some of whom are already committed to adopting plurilingual approaches.

Some issues remain open, such as the organisational changes needed in terms of equipment and teachers' collaboration to ensure a highly effective integration of subject-specific and language skills. At present, however, and based on the various elements gathered during the action research, we can conclude that plurilingual approaches in formal adult education programmes are not only feasible but also promisingly effective. While determining the extent to which these approaches support learning requires further investigation (including experimental or quasi-experimental studies), at present it is certainly clear that they create an inclusive environment in which students' prior experiences and knowledge can come to the fore as the basis for the acquisition of new and further knowledge, and one in which ascribed identity labels are challenged.

Further studies on their reception by teachers and students, and a more comprehensive and analytical breakdown of curricula can support positive future developments.

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